

ENHANCING EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT AND SATISFACTION THROUGH STRATEGIC TALENT ACQUISITION AND MARKETING INTEGRATION

Saithu Mohammed, SRM Institute of Science & Technology,
Kattankulathur

Jain Jacob, SRM Institute of Science & Technology, Kattankulathur

Maheswari P., SRM Institute of Science & Technology, Kattankulathur

Ranjitha Ragu, Pondicherry University

Mailanchikeel Ebrahim, Pondicherry University

ABSTRACT

This study is an attempt to focus on the role of talent acquisition and employee engagement in enhancing job satisfaction, more particularly in Indian IT companies. In this paper, a descriptive type of research methodology is used, in which a survey was administered to 165 employees belonging to different IT companies.

Key findings demonstrate that effective talent acquisition strategies have a great impact on employee engagement and satisfaction, hence leading to improved organizational effectiveness. The correlation between talent acquisition and job satisfaction was weak and negative, thus proving that some practices may not enhance satisfaction. On the contrary, strong positive association was realized between the variables of employee engagement and job satisfaction, which proves that high engagement is related to high job satisfaction. Further, the demographic factors identified were found to influence talent acquisition, engagement, and satisfaction levels greatly and hence require tailored HR strategies.

The paper concludes by recommending that organizations fine-tune the talent acquisition process in a manner that aligns the employee engagement strategy. Developing a strategic approach toward recruiting and retaining workers will better place an organization in the marketplace to compete for current and future talent and enhance performance and competitiveness.

Keywords: Talent Acquisition, Employee Engagement, Job Satisfaction, IT Industry, Human Resource Management, Organizational Performance.

JEL Classification: M54, J28, J24.

INTRODUCTION

Of late, the effective management of human resources is recognized as one of the critical elements in the achievement of sustainable success within the modern competitive business environment. The study investigates the intertwined roles of talent acquisition and employee engagement on job satisfaction and how they interact to influence the outcomes of the organization.

Talent acquisition is the strategic process of identification, attraction, and hiring of people with skills that fit the goals and culture of the company. Effective talent acquisition guarantees that organisations can build a workforce that is competent enough to innovate and meet business objectives (Han & Han, 2009). Through data analytics, social media, and

employer branding, organisations could develop better ways to acquire the right kind of talent to compete in this global arena (Collings & Mellahi, 2009).

Emotional commitment and enthusiasm of employees towards work and organization are core determinants of job satisfaction. Higher levels of employee engagement provide a more productive and job-satisfied workforce, which finally reflects in the culture of the organization. Employee engagement can be achieved by providing them with a supportive work environment that offers growth opportunities and appreciates their contribution.

Employee engagement, the emotional commitment and enthusiasm employees have towards their work and organization, plays a pivotal role in shaping job satisfaction. Engaged employees are more productive, demonstrate higher levels of job satisfaction, and contribute positively to the organizational culture (Harter et al., 2002). Engaging employees involves fostering a supportive work environment, offering growth opportunities, and recognizing their contributions (Robinson et al., 2004).

Job satisfaction can be described as the level by which workers in the organization feel contented and pleased with their jobs. Some of the aspects that entail job satisfaction include work environment, remunerations, career growth prospects, and work-life balance (Locke, 1976). Reduced turnover, increased retention, and better performance would be noted in the organization when employees have a higher rate of job satisfaction (Judge et al., 2001).

The relationship linking talent acquisition, employee engagement, and eventually job satisfaction is complex and very important. The bottom line of effective talent acquisition is that it brings onboard individuals who are not only talented but also culturally fitting; this lays the foundation for higher levels of engagement. When employees are engaged and feel valued, then their level of job satisfaction will increase, and as a result of that, they will perform better with reduced cases of turnover. This study therefore seeks to explore these dynamics by investigating how strategic talent acquisition practices influence employee engagement and eventually lead to an increase in job satisfaction.

These relationships are important to understand for any organization looking to enhance its human resource practices for betterment in overall organizational health. Effective management of talent acquisition and employee engagement could work toward a more satisfied and productive workforce. This research adds insight into the mechanisms by which these factors interplay, providing an overall framework for enhancing job satisfaction through strategic HR management.

Statement of Problem

The rising complexity and competitiveness of the current business environment necessitate a more strategic approach to human resource management. While much research has been conducted on the independent variables of talent acquisition, employee engagement, and job satisfaction, very few studies have been conducted on their relationships. Organizations many a time face serious challenges with regard to the effective recruitment of talented employees, maintenance of high levels of employee engagement, and assurance of satisfaction with the job. All these challenges impact overall performance, productivity, and retention rates.

It is against this backdrop that the present research endeavors to fill this gaping void by examining how strategic talent acquisition and robust practices of employee engagement synergistically drive job satisfaction. The study therefore explores the interconnectedness of these key HR functions with a view to eliciting useful insights toward a more coherent and effective approach to human resource management. That is what is needed for holistic understanding in organizations seeking improved competitive advantage, a motivated

workforce, and long-term sustainable success in the business environment, which keeps on changing.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the relationship between the demographics of the employees and job outcomes
- To understand the role of talent acquisition and employee engagement on job satisfaction

Research Questions

1. How do demographic factors of employees relate to job outcomes such as job satisfaction and employee engagement?
2. To what extent does employee engagement predict job satisfaction among employees?
3. How does the effectiveness of talent acquisition processes relate to employee engagement and job satisfaction?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between demographics of employees and the study variables.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between talent acquisition practices, employee engagement and job satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Probably the most critical interaction in human resource management is between talent acquisition, employee engagement, and job satisfaction. Talent acquisition—the process of attracting and selecting people who best fit the organization clears the way toward employee engagement and eventual job satisfaction. In this regard, successful talent acquisition strategies ensure that new hires not only have the right skills but also fit well in the culture of an organization, thereby enhancing their level of engagement right from the start (Collings & Mellahi, 2009). If the employees feel they are well fitted to the job and to the organization, they will be more engaged and satisfied with their jobs.

Employee engagement refers to emotional and cognitive investments by employees in their work; therefore, it is among the leading predictors of job satisfaction. Because their work has meaning and they feel valued by the organization, their attitude is more likely to include portrayals of relatively high job satisfaction (Harter et al., 2002). The factors that enhance engagement are opportunities for professional development, positive feedback, supportive leadership, and good work environment (Robinson et al., 2004).

The relationship between talent acquisition, employee engagement, and job satisfaction is cyclical and mutually reinforcing. High-quality talent acquisition means drawing in people who are more likely to become engaged employees, while the engaged employees will in turn report higher job satisfaction. Job satisfaction will then contribute to reduced cases of turnover and increased organizational performance (Locke, 1976; Judge et al., 2001).

This could then have a positive effect on employee engagement if the strategic talent acquisition process focused on cultural fit and alignment of organizational values in hiring. That is, the more aligned a new hire is with the organization culture and values, the more sense of belonging and purpose that will be built, which is important for its sustained engagement and satisfaction (Collings & Mellahi, 2009). The reason being, employees who are engaged are likely to be satisfied with their jobs since they have the feeling that their efforts are recognized and valued, hence giving them a more enriching work experience (Harter et al. 2002).

Understanding the dynamics among employee demographics, talent acquisition, employee engagement, and job satisfaction is therefore valuable in improving human resource practices in organizations. Coupled with an organizational culture of engagement, strategic acquisitions of talent are sure ways to significantly enhance job satisfaction and improve overall organizational performance.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Pioneers such as (Emerson, 1976) in their substantial development of Social Exchange Theory have laid down a strong base for comprehending the links among organizational belongings, employee attitudes as well as job outcomes. SET is a theoretical paradigm that states that social behavior is the product of an exchange process that aims at maximizing benefits and minimizing costs. In the context of organizational behavior, the theory argues that workers acquire direct reports through mutual relationships with their employers involving trade-off with their time, effort as well as commitment for the organizations' tangible and intangible rewards. By and large, Social Exchange Theory is a most valuable viewpoint through which the relationships between talent acquisition, employee engagement, and the satisfaction of job could be explained. Hence, it implies a relationship which is more of a two-way transaction where there is a balance or an upper/lower hand between the give and take of employees' ideas and behavior with the organization. The proposed framework helps in guiding through finding what organizations need to improve talent acquisition like the setting of expectations, employee engagement, and eventually job satisfaction.

METHODOLOGY

The present study aimed to explore the nexus between talent acquisition practices, employee engagement, and job satisfaction in Indian IT companies. The sample comprised 165 employees from different companies of Indian IT organizations, ranging across executives, top management, and middle-level managers. We used a snowball sampling method for participant recruitment. Anonymized demographic data were collected from each participant.

An exhaustive literature search was done to develop a structured questionnaire using objective scales after content, face, and construct validity. We scored all items using a 5-point Likert scale. The questionnaire comprised two major parts: Talent Acquisition - As adapted. It contained, for example, the item "How satisfied were you with the recruiting process in our company?" and "With how steep of a curve do you believe our organization's talent acquisition practices are aligned with its ambitions?"

Employee Engagement and Job Satisfaction has been constituted with items from two different sources: a) Employee Engagement: Based on (Al-Dalahmeh et al., 2018), with sample items of "How often do you feel enthusiastic about your job?" and "To what extent do you feel intensively occupied by your work? b) Job Satisfaction: Adapted, with sample items "How satisfied are you with your current role and responsibilities?" and "How well is your job meeting your expectations?"

The scale items were first examined through a reliability analysis. Calculated Cronbach's alpha for all items exceeded 0.70, hence representing strong internal consistency. Each respondent was given a personal questionnaire. The nature of the research and their rights as respondents was explained to them by the researcher. The questionnaires were collected directly from them after they filled it up for privacy purposes. For data analysis, statistical tools such as percentage analysis, correlation analysis, and Analysis of Variance-ANOVA-and t-Test have been used.

RESULTS

The analysis aimed to assess the relationship between employee demographics and three key organizational variables: Talent Acquisition (TA), Employee Engagement (EE), and Job Satisfaction (JS) and the relationship between these study variables. First, We hypothesized no significant differences across demographic categories for any of the study variables (H_{01}).

One-way ANOVA revealed significant variations in TA ($F(4, 55) = 4.763, p = .002$), EE ($F(4, 55) = 37.407, p < .001$), and JS ($F(4, 55) = 62.660, p < .001$) based on employee age groups. Similarly, significant effects were observed for qualification levels (TA: $F(2, 57) = 6.110, p = .004$; EE: $F(2, 57) = 52.461, p < .001$; JS: $F(2, 57) = 23.031, p < .001$) and income ranges (TA: $F(3, 56) = 3.203, p = .030$; EE: $F(3, 56) = 88.446, p < .001$; JS: $F(3, 56) = 33.514, p < .001$). These findings suggest that employee demographics significantly influence TA, EE, and JS Tables 1 & 2.

Table 1 ANOVA			
Demographic	Talent Acquisition (F, p)	Employee Engagement (F, p)	Job Satisfaction (F, p)
Age	$F(4, 55) = 4.763, p = .002$	$F(4, 55) = 37.407, p < .001$	$F(4, 55) = 62.660, p < .001$
Qualification	$F(2, 57) = 6.110, p = .004$	$F(2, 57) = 52.461, p < .001$	$F(2, 57) = 23.031, p < .001$
Income Range	$F(3, 56) = 3.203, p = .030$	$F(3, 56) = 88.446, p < .001$	$F(3, 56) = 33.514, p < .001$
Experience Level	$F(4, 55) = 2.492, p = .054$	$F(4, 55) = 41.866, p < .001$	$F(4, 55) = 106.955, p < .001$

Experience level exhibited a significant relationship with EE ($F(4, 55) = 41.866, p < .001$) and JS ($F(4, 55) = 106.955, p < .001$). However, the effect on TA ($F(4, 55) = 2.492, p = .054$) approached but did not reach statistical significance.

Table 2 INDEPENDENT SAMPLES T-TEST			
Category	Talent Acquisition (t, p)	Employee Engagement (t, p)	Job Satisfaction (t, p)
Gender	$t(58) = -2.170, p = .034$	$t(58) = -5.725, p < .001$	$t(58) = -3.931, p < .001$
Marital Status	$t(58) = -2.586, p = .012$	$t(58) = 9.410, p < .001$	$t(58) = 6.185, p < .001$
Employment Type	$t(58) = 0.116, p = .908$	$t(58) = -3.356, p = .001$	$t(58) = -1.965, p = .054$

Independent samples t-tests further revealed significant gender differences for all variables (TA: $t(58) = -2.170, p = .034$; EE: $t(58) = -5.725, p < .001$; JS: $t(58) = -3.931, p < .001$). Marital status categories displayed similar patterns (TA: $t(58) = -2.586, p = .012$; EE: $t(58) = 9.410, p < .001$; JS: $t(58) = 6.185, p < .001$). Interestingly, only EE showed a significant difference ($t(58) = -3.356, p = .001$) between permanent and temporary employees. TA ($t(58) = 0.116, p = .908$) and JS ($t(58) = -1.965, p = .054$) showed no significant and marginally non-significant effects for employment type, respectively.

This study investigated the interrelationships between talent acquisition (TA), employee engagement (EE), and job satisfaction (JS), with a specific focus on the hypothesis

proposing no significant relationships between these variables (H_{02}). Correlation analysis revealed a complex relationship between the variables.

A weak negative correlation emerged between TA and JS ($r = -0.160$, $p = 0.222$). However, this association lacked statistical significance, suggesting insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis for this specific pairing.

In contrast, a statistically significant ($p = 0.019$) and weak negative correlation was observed between TA and EE ($r = -0.303$). This finding indicates a potential inverse relationship, where certain talent acquisition practices might be associated with lower employee engagement.

The relationship between EE and JS presented a different picture. A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.633$, $p < 0.001$) emerged, highlighting a statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) and strong association between employee engagement and job satisfaction. This suggests that engaged employees tend to report higher levels of job satisfaction Table 3.

		Talent Acquisition	Deployment	Employee Engagement	Job Satisfaction
TA	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	60			
EE	Pearson Correlation	-.303*	.249	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.019	.055		
	N	60	60	60	
JS	Pearson Correlation	-.160	.370**	.633**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.222	.004	.000	
	N	60	60	60	60

Furthermore, deployment practices (DP) also demonstrated a weak positive correlation with JS ($r = 0.370$, $p = 0.004$), significant at the 0.01 level. This unexpected finding suggests that deployment strategies may also influence employee job satisfaction.

To delve deeper into the relationship between EE and JS, a regression analysis was conducted. The results revealed that employee engagement explains approximately 40.07% ($R\text{-squared} = 0.4007$) of the variance in job satisfaction. This indicates that EE serves as a significant predictor of JS within this model.

In conclusion, our analyses yielded mixed results regarding the hypotheses (H_{01} and H_{02}). While employee demographics significantly influenced Talent Acquisition (TA), Employee Engagement (EE), and Job Satisfaction (JS) (H_{01}) in most cases, exceptions were found in TA for both experience and employment type. These findings highlight the importance of considering demographic diversity in human resource strategies.

For the relationships between TA, EE, and JS (H_{02}), the null hypothesis was partially rejected. We observed a significant negative association between TA and EE, suggesting that certain talent acquisition practices might be linked to lower employee engagement. Conversely, a significant positive correlation emerged between EE and JS, indicating that engaged employees report higher job satisfaction. Deployment practices also emerged as a potential factor influencing job satisfaction.

DISCUSSION

The study investigated the relationship between the employees' demographics with three crucial organization variables, namely: Talent Acquisition (TA), Employee Engagement (EE), and Job Satisfaction (JS). The findings from the research highlight significant

interactions of these variables, and the implications are heavy in nature for both human resource practices and theoretical perspectives.

One-way ANOVA results showed significant variation, with regard to TA, EE, and JS across demographic groups namely age, level of qualification, and income brackets. This is indicative that demographic factors are potent in altering these organizational outcomes. For instance, older workers may show different levels of engagement and job satisfaction compared to their younger colleagues, as previous studies have also shown that age-related factors significantly influence job satisfaction (Kooij et al., 2010). In addition, the impact of educational background on employee engagement and job satisfaction highlights the importance of education level in shaping the nature of job performance and satisfaction. An earlier study by (Ng & Feldman, 2010) also established that with increasing education, job satisfaction and commitment to the organization also increase.

The experience level exhibited a significant relationship with EE and JS but not with TA, which approached but did not reach statistical significance. This finding implies that while experienced employees tend to be more engaged and satisfied, their experience does not necessarily affect the organization's ability to attract new talent. This aligns with findings by (Maden, 2015), who noted that experienced employees often have higher job satisfaction due to better role clarity and reduced job stress. The lack of significant influence on TA suggests that other factors, such as organizational reputation and recruitment strategies, might play a more critical role in attracting talent.

Independent samples t-tests revealed significant gender differences in TA, EE, and JS, indicating that men and women might experience these organizational variables differently. This aligns with previous studies that have documented gender disparities in job satisfaction and engagement (Chiu & Kosinski, 1999). For instance, women might experience higher job satisfaction in supportive and inclusive work environments, highlighting the need for gender-sensitive HR policies. The significant impact of marital status on TA, EE, and JS further emphasizes the role of personal life stability in workplace dynamics, as also noted by (Clark, 1997), who found that married employees often report higher job satisfaction due to better work-life balance.

The research showed that permanent and temporary employees significantly differed in EE but not on TA or JS. This would imply that job security becomes the pertinent factor in determining the level of engagement, as similarly reported by (De Cuyper et al., 2008). They found that permanent employees usually have higher levels of engagement, having job security and better career prospects, whereas temporary employees may feel less committed to the organization. The lack of significant difference in TA and JS between permanent and temporary employees suggests that other factors might play a more considerable role in these areas, such as job role and work environment.

The analysis of the correlations showed a weak negative correlation between TA and JS, not statistically significant, implying inadequate evidence to reject the null hypothesis of no relationship between these variables. This implies that talent acquisition practices do not have a significant impact on job satisfaction, a finding contradicting some studies while agreeing with others like (Hausknecht, 2015), who reported mixed effects of talent acquisition on organizational outcomes. By contrast, the correlation was weakly negative between TA and EE and statistically significant, which could suggest that certain practices of TA lower employee engagement. This again points to a need for balance within the approach of the TA processes so as not to create disengagement for current employees, as also supported by research from (Chapman et al., 2005).

The relationship between EE and JS presented a moderate positive correlation, indicating that higher engagement levels are associated with greater job satisfaction. Such findings are consistent with a considerable amount of literature that places engagement as one

important factor affecting job satisfaction (Harter et al., 2002; Kular et al., 2008). Thus, the engaged employee is likely to consider his or her job more meaningful and rewarding, hence have higher job satisfaction. This highlights the significance of allocating resources towards employee engagement initiatives to enhance job satisfaction and minimize turnover rates.

The study also discovered that the correlation between DP and JS was positive and weak, significant at 0.01 levels. This unexpected finding suggests that how employees are allocated and managed within the organization can influence their satisfaction with their job. These findings corroborate earlier work by (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007) that emphasized job resources, including deployment practices, as one of the facilitators to employee well-being and job satisfaction. Effective deployment strategies can make sure that employees fit their jobs well, improving job satisfaction.

The findings regarding the relationship between TA, EE, and JS also align with Social Exchange Theory (SET). The weak negative correlation between TA and EE suggests that certain talent acquisition practices may create a perceived imbalance in the exchange relationship for current employees, leading to lower engagement. This underscores the need for organizations to carefully manage TA processes to maintain a positive exchange relationship with existing employees (Chapman et al., 2005). Conversely, the positive correlation between EE and JS indicates that when employees perceive their engagement efforts are reciprocated with job satisfaction, the exchange relationship is strengthened, leading to higher overall satisfaction (Harter et al., 2002; Kular et al., 2008).

In conclusion, the analyses yielded mixed results regarding the hypotheses. While employee demographics significantly influenced TA, EE, and JS in most cases, exceptions were found for TA in relation to experience and employment type. The findings highlight the importance of considering demographic diversity in HR strategies. The relationships between TA, EE, and JS revealed that certain TA practices might be linked to lower employee engagement, while high engagement levels are associated with greater job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

The analysis highlighted significant relationships between employees' demographic factors and organizational aspects of Talent Acquisitions, Employee Engagement, and Job Satisfaction. The study found that demographic variables such as age, educational background, and earning income significantly impact these variables. It was also brought about by the correlation that some Talent Acquisition practices may negatively impact Employee Engagement, while Employee Engagement was found to positively relate to Job Satisfaction. Deployment practices that were effective also enhanced JS in a way that is consistent with Social Exchange Theory, which posits that reciprocal relationships between employees and employers influence workplace outcomes.

Practical Implications

The present study highlights various key areas that are in crucial need of development within the HR practices. Development and enhancement of the areas of TA, EE, and JS would require a shaping of the HR policies with the existing demographic variation within the employees. Policies for the development of engagement, which are age-group- and qualification-based engagement development policies, would be more effective rather than a single blanket approach.

Second, such HR policies will help address the identified disparities in TA, EE, and JS between men and women through gender-sensitive practices. This can be a good avenue to provide an inclusive and supportive environment that would eventually improve job satisfaction for all employees.

The findings also highlight the importance of job security, particularly for temporary workers. Job stability provides reasons for organizations to enhance employee commitment and satisfaction levels. However, it is necessary to strike a balance in terms of hiring talent. Human resource policies should not negatively affect the commitment of the existing employees. In this context, a positive exchange relationship should be maintained with the current employees.

Suggestions for Future Research

Longitudinal studies may be designed to determine when and up to what extent changes in the demographics over time are related to TA, EE, and JS. This perhaps represents a greater understanding of how such relationships operate, emphasizing how changes in labor composition impact a range of human resource outcomes.

Sectors analyses can also be done in a study of demographic factors and organizational variables across industries. This would help to highlight the best-fit human resource practices for a given sector. The procedures to engage a millennial workforce in the technology industry could well be much different from those that would work in a manufacturing setup.

Third, intervention studies can be developed to assess the efficacy of selected human resource practices on talent acquisition, employee engagement, and job satisfaction in different demographic cohorts. These would then provide evidence-based suggestions for HR practices that enable organizations to contextualize their strategies in ways that maximize their impact across diverse segments of employees.

Future studies would benefit from incorporating cultural differences as an added moderating factor in the relationship among TA, EE, and JS. This cultural understanding, then, of multinational organizations, can develop culturally sensitive HR strategies. In so doing, organizations will be in better preparation to devise inclusive and effective human resources practices worldwide by understanding how cultural norms and values shape employees' experiences.

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